

STUDIES ON 'LIPASE' FROM OIL SEEDS. PART IX. COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE LIPASES FROM DIFFERENT OIL SEEDS

By C. V. RAMAKRISHNAN AND G. V. NEVGI

A comparative study of the lipases prepared from castor, safflower and sesame seeds has been made.

An attempt has been made to get a sample of lipase which is more active than castor lipase. So the lipase was extracted from sesame (*Sesamum indicum*) and safflower seeds (*Carthamus tinctorius*) and their activities compared with that of castor lipase.

The lipases of castor seed, sesame and safflower were prepared according to Longnecker and Haly's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2019) and used for the experiments.

EXPERIMENTAL

Effect of the Nature of the Buffer and the Nature of the Substrate on the Activity of Lipases from the Three Seeds

The effect of different buffers on the activity of the lipase and the optimum p_H in case of each buffer have been studied in different oils like olive oil, castor oil, sesame oil and safflower oil in order to ascertain the effect of the nature of the buffer as well as the nature of the substrate on the optimum p_H of the lipase.

The three buffers : disodium phosphate - citric acid, sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer mixtures of different p_H were prepared according to McIlvaine and Walpole's methods (*J. Biol. Chem.* 1921, 49, 183) respectively and used for the experiment.

Each set of the experiments consisted of different oil (1 c.c.), water (2 c.c.), different lipases (0.1 g.), different buffer (5 c.c.) of varying p_H and a few drops of toluene in a conical flask, corked well and incubated for 24 hours at 37°. Always a blank accompanied each sample. After the period of incubation, each flask was taken out and the contents titrated against $N/10$ -NaOH. The results are given in the following tables.

From the tables below, it is found that in case of castor seed lipase, the optimum p_H is 4.8 in disodium phosphate-citric acid and sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer and 4.9 in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (variation being negligible) irrespective of the nature of the oil used as a substrate. The maximum percentage hydrolysis of the oil by castor seed lipase decreases in the order : castor oil, olive oil, sesame oil and safflower oil. As regards the nature of the buffer, the activity is always more in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer and less in case of disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer.

In case of sesame lipase, the optimum p_H is always 5.5. The maximum percentage hydrolysis decreases in the order : sesame oil, olive oil, castor oil and safflower oil.

TABLE I

Buffer : disodium phosphate-citric acid.

Diff. bet the sample and the blank in terms of c. c. of $N/10$ -NaOH in case of

Set No.	pH .	Castor lipase.	Sesame lipase.	Safflower lipase.	Castor lipase.	Sesame lipase.	Safflower lipase.
		Olive oil (1 c.c.).			Castor oil (1 c.c.).		
1	2.4	3.1	1.9	1.2	4.2	0.9	0.5
2	2.8	4.8	2.2	1.7	5.0	1.2	0.8
3	3.1	4.9	2.6	2.0	7.6	1.8	1.1
4	4.8	5.0	3.0	2.4	8.0	2.5	1.4
5	5.2	0.7	3.1	2.7	3.4	2.7	1.7
6	5.5	0.5	3.8	3.0	2.8	3.1	1.9
7	5.7	1.0	2.9	3.4	2.6	2.6	2.8
8	6.2	0.2	2.2	2.5	2.1	2.1	2.0
		Sesame oil (1 c.c.).			Safflower oil (1 c.c.).		
1	2.4	2.1	2.2	0.9	1.5	0.8	0.9
2	2.8	2.6	2.5	1.1	1.7	1.1	1.2
3	3.1	2.9	2.8	1.5	1.9	1.3	1.5
4	4.8	3.8	3.0	1.7	2.1	1.5	1.9
5	5.2	0.3	3.3	2.0	0.2	1.9	2.2
6	5.5	0.2	4.2	2.2	0.2	2.9	2.8
7	5.7	0.2	3.8	3.0	0.1	2.1	3.7
8	6.2	0.1	3.5	2.7	0.1	1.8	3.3

TABLE II

Buffer : sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid.

Diff. bet. the sample and the blank in terms of c. c. of $N/10$ -NaOH in case of

Set No.	pH .	Castor lipase.	Sesame lipase.	Safflower lipase.	Castor lipase.	Sesame lipase.	Safflower lipase.
		Olive oil (1 c.c.).			Castor oil (1 c.c.).		
1	1.5	0.9	1.1	0.7	1.5	0.5	0.4
2	2.9	7.9	1.5	1.2	8.2	1.1	0.8
3	3.8	13.8	2.3	1.8	15.6	1.6	1.2
4	4.3	15.3	3.4	2.3	18.8	2.2	1.4
5	4.8	19.6	5.2	2.0	22.6	2.9	1.8
6	5.2	2.5	6.1	3.1	10.1	3.2	2.0
7	5.5	2.2	7.1	3.7	7.8	5.8	2.4
8	5.7	1.6	5.7	4.8	5.2	4.0	3.8
9	6.0	1.1	4.2	4.2	2.3	3.5	2.7

TABLE II (contd.)

Diff. bet. the sample and the blank in terms of c. c. of $N/10\text{-NaOH}$ in case of

Set No.	pH	Castor lipase.	Sesame lipase.	Safflower lipase.	Castor lipase.	Sesame lipase.	Safflower lipase.
		Sesame oil (1 c.c.).			Safflower oil (1 c.c.).		
1	1.5	2.4	1.2	0.5	1.4	0.5	0.4
2	2.9	3.5	2.5	0.9	2.8	0.8	1.1
3	3.8	7.8	3.8	1.1	5.4	1.2	1.8
4	4.3	11.2	4.1	1.8	9.5	1.9	2.3
5	4.8	15.2	4.9	2.1	12.2	2.8	3.1
6	5.2	10.5	5.3	2.3	10.1	3.1	3.9
7	5.5	9.8	9.8	2.9	8.5	4.5	4.2
8	5.7	7.2	6.5	4.1	8.0	4.3	5.2
9	6.0	5.9	5.2	3.4	7.2	3.9	4.8

TABLE III

Buffer: sodium acetate-acetic acid.

Diff. bet. the sample and the blank in terms of c.c. of $N/10\text{-NaOH}$ in case of

Set No.	pH	Castor lipase.	Sesame lipase.	Safflower lipase.	Castor lipase.	Sesame lipase.	Safflower lipase.	
		Olive oil (1 c.c.).			Castor oil (1 c.c.).			
1	3.8	7.1	1.2	0.8	6.4	1.2	0.8	
2	4.1	11.2	2.4	1.1	12.9	2.3	1.1	
3	4.8	15.8	3.6	1.6	21.8	3.8	1.8	
4	4.9	31.7	4.8	2.4	38.4	4.1	2.0	
5	5.5	10.5	9.2	3.8	25.6	6.5	2.5	
6	5.7	7.3	7.5	5.7	20.2	5.2	4.2	
7	5.9	5.8	6.2	4.1	18.9	4.3	3.8	
8	6.0	4.3	6.0	3.9	17.2	3.9	3.1	
		Sesame oil (1 c.c.).			Safflower oil (1 c.c.).			
1	3.8	3.8	2.9	0.9	3.2	1.2	1.9	
2	4.1	7.9	3.2	1.8	5.7	1.8	2.4	
3	4.8	12.5	4.7	2.3	11.5	2.1	3.1	
4	4.9	18.3	5.8	3.4	16.8	3.5	3.9	
5	5.5	14.3	11.2	3.8	14.3	5.8	5.0	
6	5.7	12.1	9.1	4.9	12.8	4.2	6.8	
7	5.9	10.1	8.7	4.5	11.6	3.9	4.9	
8	6.0	9.7	8.3	4.1	10.9	3.2	3.7	

In case of safflower lipase, the optimum p_H is 5.7. The maximum percentage hydrolysis decreases in the order: safflower oil, olive oil, sesame oil and castor oil. Thus, the optimum p_H in case of castor, sesame and safflower lipases are 4.8 (or 4.9), 5.5 and 5.7 *i.e.*, each lipase has got its own optimum p_H . Further, they do not change either with the nature of the oil or with that of the buffer used. The activity is always the least in disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer and more in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer in all cases. In case of each lipase, there is maximum hydrolysis in its own oil and olive oil in general is a good substrate.

Effect of Buffer Concentration on the Enzymic Hydrolysis of Olive Oil

The hydrolysis of olive oil was carried out using different concentrations of sodium acetate-acetic buffer of p_H 4.9 and the three kinds of lipases in order to study the effect of change of buffer concentration on the enzymic hydrolysis. The amount of buffer added was varied from 1 to 7 c.c.

Each set of the experiments consisted of olive oil (1 c.c.), water (2 c.c.), different lipases (0.1 g.) and varying quantities of acetate buffer of p_H 4.9 and incubated for 24 hours at 37°. Always the blank was carried out. After the period of incubation, the contents of each flask were titrated against $N/10$ -NaOH after adding 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE IV

Oil taken = 1 c.c.

Set No.	Buffer added.	Diff. in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH between the sample & the blank for		
		Castor lipase.	Sesame lipase.	Safflower lipase.
1	1.0 c.c.	29.1	4.0	3.4
2	2.0	23.2	3.6	3.0
3	3.0	18.4	2.8	2.6
4	4.0	16.0	2.3	2.3
5	5.0	14.9	1.8	2.0
6	6.0	12.3	1.4	1.8
7	7.0	11.0	0.7	1.6

From the results it is found that the percentage hydrolysis is the maximum at the concentration of 1 c.c. and goes on decreasing with the increase of buffer concentration.

Effect of Substrate Concentration on the Hydrolysis of Olive Oil

The hydrolysis of olive oil was carried out using the three different kinds of lipases by changing the concentration of the oil and keeping the other quantities constant in order to study the effect of the substrate concentration on the enzymic hydrolysis of olive oil.

Each set of the experiments consisted of varying quantities of olive oil, water (2 c.c.), different lipases (0.1 g.) and 1 c.c. of acetate buffer of 4.9 pH , incubated for 24 hours at 37°. After the period of incubation, the contents were titrated against $N/10$ -NaOH after the addition of 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol and warming for some time. Always each set was accompanied by a blank. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE V

Diff. in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH bet. the sample and the blank for

Set No.	Oil in c.c.	castor lipase.	sesame lipase.	safflower lipase.
1	1.0	41.8	3.4	2.1
2	2.0	49.2	3.9	2.8
3	3.0	56.1	5.2	3.7
4	4.0	53.2	4.9	3.6
5	5.0	47.0	4.7	3.6
6	6.0	41.3	4.0	3.4

In all the three cases the percentage hydrolysis of the oil increases with the substrate concentration from 1 to 3 c.c. and after 3 c.c. it begins to decrease. Therefore, the maximum hydrolysis is obtained when the concentration of the oil is 3 c.c.

Effect of Enzyme Concentration on the Hydrolysis of Olive Oil

The hydrolysis of olive oil by the three kinds of lipase was carried out using different concentrations of the enzyme and keeping other quantities constant in order to study the effect of enzyme concentration on the olive oil.

Each set of the experiments consisted of olive oil (1 c.c.), water (2 c.c.), acetate buffer (1 c.c.) and varying quantities of the enzyme lipase and incubated at 37° for 24 hours. After the period of incubation, the contents were titrated against $N/10$ -NaOH after the addition of 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol and warming for sometime. Always a blank experiment was carried out in each case. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE VI

Oil taken = 1 c.c.

Diff. in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH bet. the sample and the blank for

Set No.	Enzyme.	castor lipase.	sesame lipase.	safflower lipase.
1	0.1 g.	36.5	3.4	2.4
2	0.2	36.7	4.2	2.7
3	0.3	37.4	5.1	3.2
4	0.4	38.3	6.5	4.5
5	0.5	44.2	7.9	6.2
6	0.6	46.8	10.2	7.8
7	0.7	49.8	11.9	10.0

From the above results, it is found that in all the three cases, the percentage hydrolysis goes on increasing as the concentration of the enzyme increases.

Change of Activity of the Lipase on Ageing

The hydrolysis of olive oil was carried out at different intervals of time using the three different lipases in order to study the effect of ageing on the activity of the lipase.

The hydrolysis of olive oil by lipases of the three seeds was studied from the time of preparation of the lipases up to a period of four and half months.

Each set of the experiments consisted of olive oil (1 c.c.), water (2 c.c.), lipase (0.1 g.) and acetate buffer (1 c.c.) and kept in the incubator at 37° for 20 minutes and then titrated against $N/10$ -NaOH. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE VII

Oil taken = 1 c.c.

Diff. bet. the sample and the blank in terms of c.c.
of $N/10$ -NaOH in case of

Set No.	Time.	castor lipase.	sesame lipase.	safflower lipase.
1	0 min.	7.5	0.2	0.2
2	20 "	7.9	0.2	0.2
3	40 "	7.9	0.2	0.3
4	1 hr.	8.4	0.3	0.3
5	24 "	13.7	0.3	0.3
6	2 days	23.2	0.4	0.3
7	3	23.3	0.5	0.5
8	4	23.4	0.5	0.5
9	5	23.5	0.6	0.5
10	6	24.4	0.6	0.5
11	8	24.8	0.8	0.7
12	11	20.5	1.0	0.7
13	15	20.2	1.2	0.7
14	23	19.9	1.4	1.1
15	71	17.9	1.2	1.1
16	78	10.7	1.2	1.1
17	85	10.2	0.9	0.9
18	93	9.8	0.8	0.9
19	100	8.9	0.4	0.7
20	114	8.6	0.4	0.7
21	121	7.8	0.1	0.5
22	134	6.5	0.0	0.4
23	142	5.1	—	0.2
24	150	3.9	—	0.0
25	160	0.5	—	—

In all the three cases, the activity increases at first and then decreases on ageing and after 160 days, almost becomes zero.

From these results it appears that these lipases cannot be used for experimental purposes since their activity changes with time. So a modification was made by preparing the acetone-dried samples of these lipases. The activities of these samples were found at different intervals of time and they gave almost a constant value, for example, 1.4, 0.8 and 0.5 in terms of c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH in case of castor, sesame and safflower lipases respectively. So, it is advisable to use acetone-dried samples of any lipase since it keeps its activity fairly constant for an approximately long time even though it is small.

Hydrolysis of Butyl Oleate by Different Lipases

The hydrolysis of butyl oleate by different lipases was carried out in ether as the solvent. Each set of the experiments consisted of 0.018 g. mol. of ester solution, 1 g. of acetone-dried lipase of each variety, 10 c.c. of ether and a few drops of toluene kept in a corked bottle. Initially 1 c.c. of it was taken and 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol added, warmed and titrated against $N/10$ -NaOH. This gave the blank reading. After keeping the mixture in the incubator at 37° at different intervals of time, 1 c.c. portion of it was taken, neutral alcohol (25 c.c.) added, warmed and titrated against $N/10$ -NaOH. From the difference in the readings for the sample and the blank, the percentage hydrolysis was calculated. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE VIII

Percentage hydrolysis on days

Lipase.	1st.	2nd.	3rd.	4th.	5th.	6th.	7th.
1. Castor	28.0	32.0	42.0	54.0	66.0	70.0	68.0
2. Sesame	7.2	10.5	15.2	23.9	25.4	24.6	—
3. Safflower	4.1	6.5	8.9	11.2	15.3	18.1	17.4

From the results the percentage hydrolysis appears to be more in case of castor lipase and less in case of safflower lipase and the activity of the lipase appears to be in the order: castor lipase, sesame lipase and safflower lipase respectively.

So, it is found that the castor lipase is only more active.

C O N C L U S I O N

A general study of the lipases obtained from oil seeds with special reference to their synthetic and hydrolytic activities has been made.

The acetone-dried lipase keeps its activity fairly constant for an appreciably long time even though their activity is low. The percentage synthesis as well as the hydrolysis of esters by lipase is independent of the number of carbon atoms in the acid and only depends upon the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol.

The difference in percentage synthesis as well as hydrolysis is observed in case of normal and *iso*-esters. The percentage synthesis of the ester by lipase increases as the number of (OH) group increases in the alcohol.

The percentage synthesis of the ester is more in case of an unsaturated acid than a saturated one. The percentage synthesis of the ester is more when both the alcohol and the acid used are aromatic than when both are aliphatic. Further, the percentage synthesis is more when both alcohol and acid belong to the same family (*i e.*, aliphatic or aromatic) than one in which they belong to different families.

The percentage synthesis of the ester by lipase increases up to a certain limit as the molecular quantity of the alcohol or acid increases till the maximum is reached.

MnSO₄ acts as an accelerator, whereas K₂Cr₂O₇ acts as a retarder for the synthesis and hydrolysis of esters by lipase.

A comparative study of castor, sesame and safflower lipases has been made. The optimum p_H of the lipase is independent of the nature of the buffer and the substrate but the percentage hydrolysis of the oil is more in acetate buffer and the activity of the lipase is more in its own oil.

DEPARTMENT OF BIOCHEMISTRY,
WADIA COLLEGE, POONA.

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